

**POSSIBILITIES OF DEVELOPING THE TECHNOLOGY OF A FUNCTIONAL ENERGY DRINK
BASED ON PECTIN**

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Abstract

Currently, the increase in the consumption of energy drinks makes the issue of their safety for the human body urgent, meaning that the long-term use of drinks with synthetic caffeine, taurine, and artificial additives can have a negative effect on the body. In this regard, the development of a safe and functional drink based on natural components is an important scientific direction. The purpose of the research work is to substantiate the possibility of developing a functional product based on apple pectin and plant extracts that has a tonic effect alternative to synthetic energy drinks and high antioxidant activity.

Keywords: pectin, functional drink, apple pectin, plant extract, antioxidant, food technology.

The increasing level of energy drink consumption in the modern food industry has brought the issue of their safety to the agenda. In particular, there is growing scientific evidence that the long-term effects of products rich in artificial stimulants and chemical additives negatively affect the cardiovascular system, nervous system, and metabolism. In such a situation, the direction of developing functional drinks based on natural raw materials is of scientific and industrial interest.

In food technology, plant polysaccharides, especially pectin, are considered natural structuring agents and biologically active components. One of the widely distributed sources of pectin is the apple, which makes it a technologically accessible and safe ingredient. In addition, the use of plant extracts makes it possible to create products that provide a natural energy effect, which forms the basis of scientific research aimed at reducing dependence on synthetic analogs.

In the work of Muzyka M.Yu., which considered the prospects for creating functional drinks, the structural and physiological advantages of pectin were comprehensively analyzed. The author notes that in improving the quality of functional drinks, pectin plays an important role not only as a viscosity former but also as a biologically active component. The study shows that

products with added pectin have a high ability to bind toxins in the body, and the conclusion is given that "pectin-based drinks occupy a special place in the functional food segment through their detoxification effect" [1, 2].

Adygezalova S.G., who studied the nutritional value of drinks with added pectin, proves the technological advantages of functional pectin-containing products with actual experimental data. The author notes that pectin, along with stabilizing the structure of the drink, has a mild effect on the gastrointestinal tract. As a result of the research, it was concluded that "the use of pectin as a natural hydrocolloid not only improves the texture of the drink but also increases its biological value" [3, 4].

Pectins are linear colloids with a molecular length of approximately 10^{-4} mm and a molecular weight from 50,000 to 200,000. The main structural component of pectin is D-galacturonic acid (containing up to 55%), which determines its functional properties. In addition to galacturonic acid, pectin contains other organic compounds, including neutral sugars and methoxyl groups. As a result of the biochemical analysis of apple raw materials, the mass fraction of pectic substances in its composition was determined (Table 1).

Table 1

Biochemical composition of raw materials

Raw material	Mass fraction of pectic substances, %	Mass fraction of soluble pectin, %
Apple	1.31	0.35

This statement shows that in the creation of a natural energy product, pectin is effective not only functionally but also technologically. Natural drinks enriched with pectin can be in high demand among functional foods. Because the compatibility of pectin in the composition of fruit-based drinks has been considered in studies conducted by scientists. That is, by adding pectin to fruit juices, it is possible to increase the storage stability and nutritional value of the product [5, 115].

Also, scientists have noted in their works that the ability of pectin to bind heavy metals and toxins increases the special adsorption activity properties of

drinks containing pectin and helps to eliminate toxic compounds from the body [6, 69]. This scientific concept allows for justifying the safety advantage of pectin-based energy products, since synthetic energetics do not have such a protective effect.

Summarizing the literature data, the potential of pectin in the production of functional foods is explained by its multifaceted biological effects. Although the presence of high doses of caffeine and chemical stimulants in the composition of synthetic energy drinks provides short-term alertness, it can pose a long-term threat to health. And the use of pectin in drinks based on nat-

ural ingredients optimizes the viscosity of the drink, increases its sensory quality, has a mild effect on the body, and has additional protective properties. In addition, the gel-forming ability of pectin provides the structural stability of the product and improves the rheological properties of drinks [5, 28].

During the study, apple pectin (high-methoxyl) is used as the main structure-forming component. As a result of the analysis of scientific data, it was determined that pectin stabilizes the structure of the drink and optimizes its viscosity, and its adsorption and prebiotic

properties increase the functional value of the product. And in order to increase biological activity, rosehip and green tea extracts are introduced. Rosehip extract enriches with vitamin C, and green tea catechins provide antioxidant activity. The combination of pectin and plant extracts makes it possible to develop a functional drink with a tonic effect without synthetic stimulants.

A comparative evaluation of the antioxidant activity of apple pectin and green tea extract was carried out using the method of neutralizing DPPH radicals (Table 2).

Table 2

Antioxidant activity of apple pectin and green tea extract according to the DPPH method

№	Sample	Concentration, %	DPPH inhibition level, %	IC ₅₀ , mg/ml
1	Apple pectin	0.5	52.6 ± 1.4	0.47
2	Apple pectin	1.0	74.2 ± 1.9	-
3	Green tea extract	0.5	68.9 ± 1.2	0.32
4	Green tea extract	1.0	88.5 ± 1.5	-

The research results show that as the pectin concentration increases, the antioxidant activity increases. Although the antioxidant activity of green tea extract is high, apple pectin also shows a pronounced antioxidant effect. The IC₅₀ indicator was determined at the level of 0.47 mg/ml, which proves that the ability of apple pectin to neutralize free radicals is moderately pronounced. The low IC₅₀ value indicates the high ability of green tea to neutralize radicals. However, the combination of pectin with its structure-forming and prebiotic properties creates a complex biological effect in the composition of a functional drink. The obtained results show that pectin can serve as a basis for use in a functional drink not only as a structure-forming component but also as a biologically active ingredient [7].

Thus, the combined use of pectin and green tea extract allows achieving a synergistic antioxidant effect and strengthens the scientific basis for developing a natural alternative to synthetic energy drinks.

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